

Report on Policy Implications

CHPM2030 Deliverable D5.4

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CHPM2030

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CHPM2030 DELIVERABLE D5.4

REPORT ON POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Summary:

Deliverable is focused on social impact assessment and policy implications of the CHPM technology. A key aspect ensuring public acceptance of CHPM technology is the stakeholder engagement from the very beginning of a future CHPM project development. EU policy framework is very supportive for development of renewable energy sources and innovative low-impact mining methods. A combine innovative energy and raw materials target of CHPM technology is ahead of policies and legislative frameworks. Definitions of specific terms (EGS, EGS-orebody, etc.) and legislative unifying of both CHPM levels under one government authority will be key for CHPM development form a policy perspective.

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List of abbreviations

CapEx – capital expenditures
€/kWh – euro per kilowatt hour
CLO – Community Liaison Officer
CLC – Community Liaison Committees
CSR – Corporate Social Responsibility
CRIRSCO – Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards
CRM – The Critical Raw Materials for EU
EBRD – European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EGEC - the European Geothermal Energy Council
EGS – enhanced geothermal system
EIA – environmental impact assessment
EIP – European Innovation Partnership
ESIA – Environmental and social impact assessment
EMMP – Environmental Monitoring and Management Programme
EPFI – Equator Principles Financial Institution
GEISIR – The Geothermal Engineering Integrating Mitigation of Induced Seismicity in Reservoirs
IAIA – International Association of Impact Assessment
IFC PS –International Finance Corporation Performance Standards
ISL – in-situ leaching
ISR – in-situ recovery

JORC – Joint Ore Reserve Committee
KWh – kilowatt hour
MW – megawatt
MW_e – megawatt
NGOs – non-governmental organisations
NTS – Non-technical Summary
OpEx – operational expenditures
PAP – project-affected people
RED – Renewable Energy Directive
REDP – Renewable Energy Development Programme
REE – rare earth elements
REF – Renewable Energy Fund
RFP – Request for Proposal
SEA – Strategic Environmental Assessment
SEP – Social Engagement Plan
SIA – social impact assessment
SIP – Strategic Implementation Plan
SLO – social licence to operate
TOR – terms of reference
WFD – Water Framework Directive

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1 Executive Summary

Task 5.4 is focused on two parts that may be seen as two different issues for the future of CHPM technology – social impacts at one side (Task 5.4.1) and policies, legislative or other related regulations on the other side (Task 5.4.2). However, policies and politicians are elected by a society, thus the social impacts are very sensitive topics that politicians (and relevant government institutions) expressing in various policy strategies or regulatory frameworks. And the policy frameworks will be influencing directly or indirectly the future development of CHPM plant.

Sub-task 5.4.1 Social Impact Assessment is focused on describing and suggesting the ‘best practises’ that future company planning to run CHPM plant should develop to minimize social impact on project affected communities. The sequence of proposed actions for relationship of CHPM developer and stakeholders is in line with ‘social licence to operate’ (SLO) and international guidance standards (e.g. International Finance Corporation Performance Standards related to social and environmental aspects). The Social Impact Assessment Methodology is introduced based on criteria set by International Association on Impact Assessment (IAIA). A great emphasis is put on stakeholder engagement into the CHPM project via proposed Stakeholder Engagement Plan and methods of stakeholder engagement.

Sub-task 5.4.2 Policy Implications is reviewing EU policy frameworks that could have direct or indirect effect on development of the CHPM technology. In general sense, EU policy framework (including funding schemes) is very supportive for deployment of clean, non-carbon energy solutions and also innovative low-impact mining methods aiming to secure raw materials for EU sustainable growth.

EU directives related to protection of environment, water, groundwater established strict rules that should ensure the minimalization of CHPM technology impacts while are in agreement with geothermal energy development (e.g. allowance of geothermal water reinjection). Challenging would be definition of CHPM technology as it is ambiguous whether it will be regulated by Waste/Mining Waste or Industry Emission directive.

EU policy framework in ‘climate action’ sets suitable environment for development of renewable sources like geothermal. However, despite fact that EU legislation clearly define ‘geothermal energy, deep-geothermal energy, especially capital intensive EGS will need more supportive legislation and definitions on both EU and national level.

CHPM will need similar actions, especially to introduce the EGS-orebody concept to legislative definition. A combine innovative energy and raw materials aim of CHPM technology is ahead of policies and legislative frameworks that will be regulating such technology or business sector. Unifying of deep-geothermal (EGS) and innovative metal extraction methods developed in the CHPM project under one licensing authority (ideally Member state's mining authorities) and single resource ownership will be key aspects for development of the CHPM technology.

2 Introduction

2.1 Objectives and role of the CHPM2030 project

The strategic objective of the CHPM2030 project is to develop a novel technological solution (Combined Heat, Power and Metal extraction from ultra-deep ore bodies), that will help reducing Europe's dependency on the import of metals and fossil fuels while, lowering the environmental impact of the energy supply.

In the envisioned technology, an Enhanced Geothermal System (EGS) is established on a metal-bearing geological formation, which will be manipulated in a manner enabling the co-production of energy and metals. On a laboratory scale, the project aims at proving the concept that the composition and structure of ore bodies have certain characteristics that could be used as an advantage when developing an EGS.

It is also planned to verify that metals can be leached from the ore bodies in high concentrations over a prolonged period of time and this may substantially increase the economics of the EGS. The project also aims at finding proof of the concept that continuous leaching of metals will increase the performance of the system over time in a controlled way without having to use high-pressure reservoir stimulation. According to our expectations, this will provide new impetus to geothermal development in Europe. Within the scope of the project, a Roadmap will also be developed to support the pilot implementation of CHPM systems before 2030, and full-scale commercial implementation before 2050.

2.2 Scope and role of WP5

The CHPM2030 project is divided into 8 work packages; Deliverable 5.4 is part of the fifth work package (WP5) called Integrated sustainability assessment. The objective of the WP5 is to assess expected environmental, social, and economic impacts of each component of proposed CHPM infrastructure. CHPM technology is combining generation of power, both electric and heat, using a concept of the Enhanced Geothermal System (EGS) with extraction of metals utilizing a mining

method very similar to in-situ leaching (ISL) or in-situ recovery. For these technologies, some partial impacts are already known and thus the assessment of CHPM project can benefit from these experiences.

Figure 1: Infographic of the CHPM technology. Scheme of a typical EGS power plant would look very similar, one exception is in targeted geothermal reservoir, which should be metal enriched system in case of the CHPM. Electrolytic metal recovery (purple box), gas diffusion electro-precipitation metal extraction (blue-green box) are created “the metal extraction level” of the CHPM technology. The last innovation against typical EGS power plant is another technology component (salt gradient power – green box) able to generate electricity.

The work package is composed of 5 tasks:

- a) Task 5.1 Integrated sustainability assessment framework introduced a structure of WP5 and role of individual tasks on the assessment of the CHPM technology.
- b) Task 5.2 Baseline economics for energy and mineral raw materials was focused on the economic and financial issues of the CHPM technology. Gathered data served for the simulation of a modelling in D5.3 as well as input for further work in other work-packages.
- c) In the Task 5.3 Decision support for economic feasibility assessment a self-assessment tool based on system dynamic approach, allowing to assess feasibility of different CHPM scenarios was developed

- d) Task 5.4 Social Impact Assessment and policy considerations will be considering possible impacts of proposed CHPM technology for the society and policy implications will also be reviewed.
- e) Task 5.5 Environmental Impact Assessment was focused on the development of a framework for a future environmental impact assessment (EIA) for CHPM technology.
- f) Task 5.6 Ethics Assessment will be focusing on ethical issues, which needs to be considered in relation for CHPM technology.

2.3 Scope and role of Task 5.4

Task 5.4 Social Impact Assessment and policy considerations is divided into two parts: sub-task 5.4.1 Social Impact Assessment is focused on describing and suggesting the 'best practises' that future company planning to run CHPM plant should develop to minimize social impact on project affected communities. The described Social Impact Assessment and sequence of proposed actions of developer-stakeholder relationship is based on methodology and standards of international institutions. A quantitative method of Social Impact Assessment Methodology described in sub-chapter 3.4 is based on IAIA standards. Proposed stakeholder engagement plan is in line with the result of Aarhus Convention (UNECE 1998), methodology of IFC PS (International Finance Corporation Performance Standards) on Environmental and Social Sustainability, EBRD (European Bank for Reconstruction and Development) Performance Requirements and the Equator Principles Financial Institutions.

Task 5.4.2 Policy Implications is reviewing the key EU policies that may have direct or indirect effect on CHPM development. As CHPM technology aims at combining two, at first sight unrelated business activities – renewable energy production and mining (metal extraction) that are in most of the cases regulated by different legislative frameworks, the task 5.4.2 will be further divided. The first part is reviewing key EU legislative documents or strategies related to the Energy Level and Metal Extraction Level of the CHPM technology. In some cases, the regulations (e.g. environment impacts, wastes) would be influencing both levels, thus sub-chapter 4.2.3 is focusing on key EU policies and regulations for both levels of CHPM technology. Last part of the key EU policies and regulations is focusing on EU Funding Incentives.

The next chapter, 4.3 Policy implications for CHPM project development, is describing a model example of a CHPM project development from the first intention through the exploration stage to fully operational CHPM plant. Specific policy implications, opportunities and challenging issues are discussed for each stage of the project.

3 Social Impact Assessment (Task 5.4.1)

3.1 Introduction

A SIA is undertaken to help a potential development by establishing existing social baseline conditions and then to use these to predict and manage associated impacts. The purpose is to help mitigate impacts from a project based on the following mitigation strategy; to avoid, minimise, reduce and compensate as a last resort. It is also important that positive social impacts relating to CHPM schemes are maximised.

Typical positive social impacts include employment and community development projects, in addition to the energy and minerals produced having vital regional, national and sometimes international importance with a reduced carbon footprint. Geothermal energy has the potential to create a virtually limitless supply of energy requiring no fuel and minimal land footprint.

Typical concerns and possible negative social impacts include impacts on water resources; effects on land use e.g. cultural heritage, recreational land use and visual impacts; noise and disturbance; sulphur dioxide emissions; management of heat for drilling programmes; and the creation of ground subsidence and induced micro seismic events.

Whilst the specific negative and positive impacts will be unique to each site, below we have outlined the typical process for completing a SIA and how stakeholders need to be engaged throughout all stages of operations, from exploration stages to closure and decommissioning of a future CHPM plant.

The Figure 2 below outlines key aspects of obtaining an ESIA (Environmental and social impact assessment) that is in line with international guidance, notably the International Finance Corporation Performance Standards (IFC PS) relating to environmental and social requirements (International Finance Corporation 2019). Figure 2 below outlines steps in accordance with IFC PS. The SIA is a component of the wider ESIA, and integration exists in many aspects between environmental and social aspects of a project. In an ESIA, numerous sections review the crossover of environmental and social impacts, including in an ecosystems services assessment where it is considered how land users utilise ecosystems and natural resources. They will also be considered in a cumulative impact assessment and in a range of environmental and social management plans that accompany an ESIA.

Figure 2: Social and community stages in an ESIA

Table 1 below outlines a typical schedule for undertaking an SIA.

Phase 1	Site visits	Identification of and engagement with key stakeholders. Discussions start with local contractors regarding social baseline collection.
	Production of the Scoping Study.	Development of plan and terms of reference (TOR) for social baseline collection following completion of the Scoping Study.
	Public consultation to present findings of the Scoping Study	Public consultation events should be carried out in accordance with IFC guidance on stakeholder engagement e.g. advertise the event well in advance and inclusivity of stakeholders.
	Produce a Social Engagement Plan (SEP).	Community Liaison Officer to ensure that the SEP is implemented at a local level.

	Commence social baseline data collection programme, including any socio-economic survey.	Collect the socio-economic baseline in collaboration with the local consultants. Local consultants collect key information required for a social baseline in line with IFC expectations. This will include socio-economic surveys undertaken within sample populations from key local communities, helping identify and understand local communities and their needs.
Phase 2	Prepare draft SIA for ESIA integrating consideration of cumulative impacts. Social contribution to Environmental Monitoring and Management Programme (EMMP) and Non-technical Summary (NTS).	Compile collected information and prepare draft ESIA document. Client feedback for review/discussion. Community liaison officer to disseminate NTS to stakeholders prior to consultation event to present the findings of the draft ESIA.
	Client review of ESIA. Finalise ESIA	Review comments from the Client.
		Discuss changes to be made.
		Complete ESIA document for submission relevant authorities.
Phase 3	Public presentation of findings of the draft ESIA to stakeholders.	Present ESIA findings to Stakeholders.
	Integration of public consultation event findings into the ESIA.	Revise consultation chapter of the ESIA and submit final version to client. ESIA is ready for publishing.

3.2 Scoping Studies

3.2.1 Phase 1 – Scoping stage

The Scoping stage will identify the main social sensitivities relating to the proposed development of a project on local communities. An important part of the process will involve identification of key stakeholders and subsequent discussions.

During the Scoping stage one of the most important aspects of international best practice is to ensure the early stakeholders' engagement. This will include preparing a Social Engagement Plan (SEP) for each project with a grievance mechanism outlined as part of this management plan. This is standard practice in accordance with the Equator Principles Financial Institution (EPFI) for the development of a Project and it will help communicate with stakeholders (Equator Principles Association 2019).

The scoping study will identify the key areas for further investigation of the social baseline and will make recommendations on any further social management plans that may be required. A scoping study will consider sensitive issues, such as resettlements that may be required for the development of a project and the likely effects on livelihoods. It will also identify key community concerns, such as risk of groundwater contamination.

Following completion of an initial Scoping Study at any site, public consultation with the company leading the project development will take place. Any public consultation events should take place in line with international best practices that include ensuring early involvement of stakeholders and timely dissemination of information on each project.

3.3 Social Baseline Development

The main focus of the social part of an ESIA will be on the land use at the site and those settlements nearest to the deposit or operational areas, though it will also assess links between local and regional activities. The wider socio-economic context should also be evaluated considering regional and national impacts of a project, including the local, regional and national financial benefits and beneficiaries.

The analysis of archive socio-economic data and subsequent verification through the collection of primary data in the socio-economic survey, the social baseline and impact assessments should consider:

3.3.1 Governance, Demography and Culture

Socio-economic background data at a local, regional and national level; information on local settlements; physical and social infrastructure in communities; local, regional and national governance; institutional influences; and the geopolitical situation in the region; including reviewing the presence and activity of NGOs operating in the area.

3.3.2 Social Infrastructure, Health and Education

The locations and key characteristics of communities around a project; physical and social infrastructure in communities; the presence of indigenous communities; inter and intra community relations; identification of vulnerable groups within communities; socio-cultural heritage and religious beliefs of communities (including the presence of sacred sites around a proposed project); health statistics in surrounding communities; housing demand and rental prices in local communities; food prices in the area; poverty levels; sources of entertainment in local communities; crime rates in local communities; and the landscape and visual character of a project area.

3.3.3 Economy and Livelihoods

Livelihoods; existing land uses and ownership; grazing rights and agricultural practices; fishing and aquaculture in the local area; occupancy rights of land; effects of land take from the Project on local people; an assessment of ethnobotany in the area; water uses by local people; the impacts of historic environmental liabilities on land users; the presence of protected areas within the local and regional area and associated land uses in these areas; local, regional and national economic background; enterprise and businesses on a local, regional and national scale; employment and income patterns in local communities including gender divisions of labour.

3.3.4 Stakeholder perceptions of the Proposed Project

Background information on consultation undertaken to date by the client. This will include gaining an understanding of how stakeholders perceive the Project and likely support levels, including assessing NGOs operating in the region and their likely views/participation on the Project.

3.4 Proposed Social Impact Assessment Methodology

This section outlines a typical social impact assessment (SIA) methodology which could be used, accounting for key differences in the socio-economic impacts compared to environmental impacts. The identification and analysis of socio-economic impacts will be informed from the site visits carried out by the local contractors, drawing and expanding on findings of the Scoping Study. Part of the SIA will include a section on stakeholder views and public consultation carried out during the ESIA process.

3.4.1 SIA Methodology

The following criteria, derived from the International Association of Impact Assessment (IAIA 2000) can be used to calculate significance of the socio-economic impacts.

Total socio-economic impact

= Q_{ti} (duration of impact) x Q_{si} (scope of impact) x Q_{ji} (intensity of impact)

Based on this calculation, the significance of the socio-economic impact is categorised into the following groups:

- Negligible: 1 to 2 (adverse or positive);
- Low: 3 to 12 (adverse or positive);
- Moderate: 13 to 31 (adverse or positive); and
- High: 32 to 64 (adverse or positive).

The potential socio-economic risk or opportunity is a function of combining the significance of the socio-economic impact with the probability of the socio-economic impact occurring.

Definitions

Impact Scope (Qsi):

This relates to the number of people affected by the impact. The following table (Table 2) contains the classifications used to quantify the scope of the impact:

Table 2: Scope of Impact (Qsi)

Scale (qualitative)	Scale (quantitative)	Score
Very low number	Less than ten people	1
Low number	Ten to one hundred people	2
Medium number	One hundred to thousand people	3
High number	More than one thousand people	4

Impact Duration (Qti):

This relates to the time period of the impact. The following table (Table 3) contains the classifications identified in order to quantify the duration of the impact:

Table 3: Duration of Impact (Qti)

Scale (qualitative)	Scale (quantitative)	Score
Short-term	Less than 6 months	1
Medium-term	Up to 1 year	2

Medium to long-term	1-10 years	3
Long-term	More than 10 years	4

Impact Intensity (Qji):

Impact intensity relates to the level of costs and benefits associated with the impact. Determination of intensity is context dependent and therefore a factor of a number of variables including; the relative cost or benefit to potentially impacted groups and individuals given their proximity, resilience, adaptability, and vulnerability. The following table (Table 4) outlines the classifications used to quantify the level of benefits and costs to impacted groups and individuals:

Table 4: Impact Intensity - Impacts (Qji)

Intensity	Score
Negligible – very low cost:benefit ratio to potentially impacted groups/individuals based on them being: distant communities/individuals that are very highly resilient and adaptable; minimal impact on identified vulnerable groups people	1
Low – low cost:benefit ratio to potentially impacted groups; distant communities that are highly resilient and adaptable; Low impacts on identified vulnerable groups people	2
Moderate – moderate cost:benefit ratio to potentially impacted groups/individuals based on them being: less distant communities/individuals that are moderately resilient and adaptable; Moderate impacts on identified vulnerable groups	3
High – high cost:benefit ratio to potentially impacted groups/individuals based on them being: close communities/individuals with low levels of resilience and adaptability; Large impacts on identified vulnerable groups people	4
Note: For positive impacts the cost:benefit ratio is reversed so	

Intensity	Score
benefit:cost is considered	

Once the total significance of the pre-mitigation / enhancement socio-economic impact has been calculated, it is reassessed using the same significance scoring but assuming that recommended mitigation or enhancement measures are in place. The purpose of the mitigation and enhancement measures is to avoid/minimise/compensate/offset the total negative socio-economic impacts or maximise the total positive socio-economic impacts. In line with the EIA methodology, the SIA methodology will be used to calculate significance of impacts for all Project activities over each phase of the Project (exploration, construction, operation and closure) with both pre and post mitigation measures in place.

The SIA will also include an assessment of Risk, which is the process of quantifying the probability of harmful effects to individuals or populations as a consequence of human activities:

$$\text{Risk} = \text{impact significance} \times \text{likelihood (probability) of occurrence}$$

To enable this calculation to be made, a categorisation of probability (likelihood) will be carried out based on: negligible, low, moderate and high. Risk has been considered in the context of socio-economic impacts, where the probability of something occurring is more easily distinguishable based on socio-economic impacts on communities. Mitigation measures for socio-economic impacts will be developed to account for risk of occurrence.

3.5 Social Licence to Operate (SLO)

It's easy to regard social responsibility or "SR" as one of the "buzz words" in today's society. The reality is, however, that the very definition of SR, has a far deeper meaning beyond the word 'social', with the ethical ideology behind its meaning relating to what defines sustainability; the triple bottom line or in essence what underpins responsible business practices. The very principles of SR, in light of 21st century global challenges, will necessitate companies paying increasing attention in how they strategise 'reducing increasing social risks' that global changes will bring. Ultimately, this provides companies have an intrinsic need to review their corporate policy to develop a game plan in how they can become more responsive to meeting the needs of local people and the wider community, both in the short and long-term.

3.6 Public Consultation and Stakeholders Engagement

The overall objective of consultation and disclosure of information is to ensure stakeholders, including local residents, about their participation in the development of the project. The IFC PSs stress that public consultation should continue throughout the entire life of the project and must be documented, demonstrating how stakeholders had the opportunity to influence Project design. Integrating stakeholder engagement into the overall ESIA is essential and the local contractor and client should develop a list of stakeholders and a SEP to satisfy IFC PSs and other good industry practice.

In order to fulfil the IFC requirements on public consultation and disclosure of information, several rounds of formal public consultation should be factored in during the ESIA process. The first will be carried out during the scoping stage and the second one following completion of the draft ESIA. The SEP should make recommendations to a client on how they should engage with project stakeholders. A Community Liaison Officer (CLO) role should be created to help increase levels of communication with stakeholders and with nearby communities. The CLO can then start the process of establishing Community Liaison Committees (CLC) within communities to assist with increasing overall engagement levels with local communities and to disseminate information more easily.

3.7 Stakeholder Identification on a project

Stakeholders are individuals, groups and organisations whose interests or rights may be affected by a proposed project, or who may have an ability to influence decisions concerning the siting, construction and operations of the project. Key stakeholders are those directly impacted (either positively or negatively) by a project.

Stakeholders are recorded in a stakeholder register in the following categories:

- Government authorities at the national, regional and local levels;
- Multi-national and international organizations (i.e., United Nations, World Bank Group, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, European Union, bilateral donors, etc.);
- Non-commercial, non-governmental and public organisations at the international, national, regional and local levels, including organised community-based organisations or interest groups (i.e., labour, youth, religious, businesses, environmental, etc.);

- Project-affected communities, including individual residents as well as non-organised groups with particular areas of interest or that may be vulnerable (i.e., elderly, people with disabilities, ethnic minorities, herders etc.);
- Commercial organizations and business associations;
- Project employees; and
- Media – at a local, regional and national level.

A stakeholder register and database should be regularly updated to demonstrate the continuous efforts made to inform stakeholders about project developments. This register forms part of a stakeholder management system to record the frequency of interaction, as well as to manage and document issues, questions and concerns about the project. These issues should be analysed and addressed as soon as possible through face-to-face meetings. A comprehensive list of issues, questions and concerns, as well as the main responses should be provided as a section of the ESIA.

Any information on additional stakeholders (individuals or groups) that may have an interest in a company's activities should be provided to the company employees. Stakeholders should be added to the database and these stakeholders should be included in future efforts to disclose public information about the project. The staff should also document issues, concerns and questions and ensure all questions are address in the final ESIA documents.

To identify stakeholders for this project, a map of each project environment should be developed indicating communities and social infrastructure in the vicinity of a project site in the context of findings from the scoping study to identify local and directly-impacted stakeholders.

In addition to monthly meetings held within identified affected communities, a CLO should regularly visit nearby communities to follow up on any issues raised, organise public events and meet with authorities or other community members. Stakeholder analysis is a dynamic and on-going process and should continue to be updated by the CLO as the understanding of stakeholders' increases and as the relationship between stakeholders and the project develops and changes. The CLO should update and keep track of the stakeholder log, stakeholder register and the database on issues, concerns and questions. Record management within the stakeholder management system is undertaken to protect personal privacy and confidentiality considerations.

3.8 Developing a Stakeholder Engagement Plan

During the exploration and feasibility phase of a project, the main aim of stakeholder

engagement has been to establish two-way communication between stakeholders at national, regional and local levels to ensure stakeholder views are incorporated into the ESIA and the project design. The SEP outlines how stakeholders will be informed of the impact assessment process and its various stages, including how they may be engaged in data collection, impact assessment and developing strategies for impact management and monitoring. During the upcoming construction and operation phases, stakeholder engagement activities will focus on keeping stakeholders informed about the project activities and to engage them in terms of monitoring and impact management.

Stakeholders are invited to review and provide feedback on this SEP. Companies should ensure these documents are available and accessible to stakeholders in suitable local languages. Stakeholders should be advised to address general enquires to the CLO, who is primarily responsible for documenting issues, concerns and questions and acts as the first point of contact.

Each project being developed involves specifically identified physical elements, aspects and facilities that are likely to generate some adverse environmental and social impacts on project-affected communities. For the purpose of an internationally compliant ESIA, each project should use a SEP to guide future engagement activities with stakeholders. Stakeholder engagement is essential to identify Project risks and impacts, accounting for concerns raised by the project-affected people (PAP) and other stakeholders. For the purpose of the SEP, PAP's are defined as individuals most likely to observe changes from environmental and social impacts of the project. This will usually be individuals who reside in the settlements closest to a project site. An ESIA will provide more explicit details on how impacts may affect different settlements and individuals.

During the exploration and feasibility phases, the main aim of stakeholder engagement is to establish two-way communication between the developer and stakeholders at national, regional and local levels to ensure stakeholder views are incorporated into the ESIA and the project design. The SEP should also outline how stakeholders will be informed of the impact assessment process and its various stages, including how they may be engaged in data collection, impact assessment and developing strategies for impact management and monitoring. During the upcoming construction and operation phases, stakeholder engagement activities should focus on keeping stakeholders informed about the project activities and to engage them in terms of monitoring and impact management.

The ESIA will provide more explicit details on how impacts may affect different settlements and individuals.

The Aarhus Convention (UNECE 1998) was ratified in January 2002 and focuses on three key areas relating to the provision of information to the public:

- **Access to information:** ensures that the public can have a system whereby one can request and receive information, thus allowing for informed participation;
- **Public participation:** provides for public participation early in decision-making on activities that can have significant environmental impact; and
- **Access to justice:** ensures that the public has legal mechanisms available to review potential violations of access to information and public participation provisions.

The Aarhus Convention differs from international standards on the basis that responsibility for disclosure, participation and access to justice resides with the host government and not the Project sponsor. However, government representatives can only fulfil the requirements of the Convention if a project sponsor has fully disclosed all information relating to environmental and social impacts. Requirements for Aarhus should be met and exceeded through the implementation of international standards.

The IFC PSs on Environmental and Social Sustainability are generally regarded as the benchmark for international accepted practice. The EBRD Performance Requirements (EBRD) have similar concepts and wording. IFC requirements for project information disclosure exceed the requirements of the European Union, as defined by the Aarhus Convention, as well as those of the local laws and regulations. The IFC PSs, which form the basis of public disclosure requirements for the Equator Principles Financial Institutions (EPFIs), stress that public consultation should be started early in Project development and that engagement with interested parties at every stage should be:

- “Free” (free of coercion, intimidation or inappropriate incentives for the affected population);
- “Prior” (timely disclosure of information to allow for meaningful influence on project implementation); and
- “Informed” (relevant, understandable and accessible information).

Specific requirements set forth in the IFC Performance Standard 1 include:

Stakeholder Analysis and Engagement Planning

- Identify affected communities and other stakeholders that may be interested in a Project and consider how external communications might facilitate a dialogue with all stakeholders; and
- Development of the SEP, including measures to allow for the effective participation of stakeholders, particularly those identified as disadvantaged or vulnerable.

Disclosure of Information

- Provision of relevant information on (i) the purpose, nature and scale of the project; (ii) duration of the proposed activities; (iii) any risks to and potential impacts on such communities and the relevant mitigation measures; (iv) the envisaged stakeholder engagement process; and (v) the grievance mechanism.

Consultation

- Undertake a process of consultation that provides affected communities with opportunities to express their views on Project risks, impacts and mitigation measures; and
- Includes a two-way process that (i) begins early in the process of identification of environmental and social impacts and continue on an on-going basis as impacts arise; (ii) is based on prior disclosure and dissemination of relevant, transparent, objective, meaningful and easily accessible information that is in a culturally appropriate local language; (iii) focuses inclusive engagement on those directly affected as opposed to those not directly affected; (iv) is free of external manipulation, interference, coercion, or intimidation; (v) enables meaningful participation where applicable; and (vi) is documented; and is tailored to the language preferences of the affected communities, their decision-making process and the needs of disadvantaged or vulnerable groups.

Informed Consultation and Participation

- Conduct an informed consultation and participation process that will result in affected communities' informed participation;
- Manages a consultation process that (i) captures both men's and women's views, if necessary through separate forums or engagements, and (ii) reflect men's and

women’s different concerns and priorities about impacts, mitigation mechanisms, and benefits, where appropriate; and

- Documents the process, in particular the measures taken to avoid or minimise risks to and adverse impacts on the affected communities and will inform those affected about how their concerns have been considered.

External Communications

- Implementation of a procedure for external communications that includes methods to (i) receive and register external communications from the public; (ii) screen and assess the issues raised and determine how to address them; (iii) provide, track and document responses; and (iv) adjust the environmental and social management programme.

Grievance Mechanism for Affected Communities

- Establish a grievance mechanism to receive and facilitate resolution of affected communities’ concerns and grievances about the environmental and social performance; and
- Inform the Affected Communities about the mechanism in the course of the stakeholder engagement process.

On-going Reporting to Affected Communities

- Provision of a schedule for periodic reports to the affected communities that describe the progress with implementation of the project action plans on issues that involved on-going impacts on affected communities and on issues that the consultation process of grievance mechanism have identified as a concern to those communities; and
- Provision of reports not less than annually.

Table 5 outlines how to document typical stakeholder concerns associated with the development of a project.

Table 5: Stakeholder Concerns regarding the development of a project
<i>Air Quality</i>

Water

Biodiversity

Soils

Seismicity

Health

Community Development

Economic viability of the Project

Processing methods

Land use

Use of local resources and employment – including employment and training opportunities

3.9 Methods of Stakeholder Engagement

This section briefly outlines the main methods of engagement that will be used in each phase of the project.

Public Hearings

Public Hearings are the basis of public disclosure in EU legislation. These formal events are conducted in close coordination with the authorities and are linked directly with the regulatory and permitting requirements for ESIA approval.

Project and Information Meetings

Project and information meetings are the most common method of engagement. Such meetings include the regular meetings that take place between staff and local authorities but may also include more formal events to disclose project updates.

Message Boards

Community message boards in local government offices should be established in the closest communities. These message boards seek to provide general information about the company and a project, as well as information on how to contact members of staff.

Community Newsletters

To enhance information dissemination in the local communities, including regular monthly newsletters and display information on the municipal offices and on government noticeboards.

Media Advertisements and Press Releases

Invitations to public hearings and other events should be issued in newspapers and radio stations, as appropriate.

Annual Updates

Each development should hold regular presentations in nearby communities. These meetings will continue past the impact assessment phase and eventually include updates on environmental and social performance during the previous year and future plans.

Grievance Mechanism

A procedure for collecting and resolving grievances is an important method that will be used throughout the project. The grievance mechanism will be publicised by all staff that have contact with external stakeholders. Community newsletters and notice boards will provide further details on the grievance mechanism and the process of registering a grievance.

3.10 Stakeholder Engagement during the ESIA Process

The ESIA stakeholder engagement is a flexible process to accommodate issues raised by concerned individuals or groups throughout the ESIA process. These will be managed by the local developer in collaboration with the independent consultant completing the ESIA where relevant. The events will take place as a series of meetings in nearby communities, at venues. Transport to all the events should be provided as required.

The draft ESIA, including a non-technical summary, should be available for public review at least 14 days prior to a meeting to discuss it. The summary will be accompanied by a *pro forma*, inviting stakeholders to comment on the draft documents by the given deadline. Comments will also be collected by e-mail or through the offices and staff.

The summary and *pro forma* will be also produced as flyers and posted to principal stakeholders in each project area, together with individual invitations to the consultation event to other key stakeholders, such as NGOs, media, company suppliers and partner organisations from outside a project area, and ministerial department representatives.

The CLO should also disseminate the planned programme for disclosure meetings in the project-affected communities via a range of communication methods. This will incorporate all identified stakeholders. Advertisements for consultation events should be provided in local languages and placed in an appropriate venue in each community (such as the administration buildings and local notice boards).

The stakeholder ESIA disclosure events themselves should comprise the presentation of the non-technical summary. At the end of the presentation, each information meeting will allow time for questions from attendees. These meetings will be documented, and minutes of the meeting should be made publicly available.

Results of information meetings held for the disclosure of the draft ESIA will be compiled and submitted as part of the final ESIA at each development. This final ESIA will demonstrate how stakeholder inputs and comments have changed the environmental and social management plans.

3.11 Grievance Mechanisms

The purpose of the grievance mechanism is to demonstrate responsiveness to stakeholder complaints and ensure stakeholder engagement throughout the project. All stakeholders are encouraged to submit written grievances to a CLO and should be reassured that submissions will not be used in any way to intimidate those submitting the complaints.

The procedure outlined below will be used to ensure the grievance mechanism is in line with international requirements.

The following questions & answers explain the grievance mechanism:

What is a "grievance"?

A grievance is a concern or complaint raised by an individual or group affected by a development/operation. Both concerns and complaints can result from either real or perceived impacts of a company's operations and may be filed in the same manner and handled with the same procedure.

What is the grievance and submission mechanism?

An official procedure through which communities and individuals affected by an activity can formally communicate their specific concerns and grievances to the company and facilitate resolutions that are mutually acceptable by the parties and within a reasonable timeframe. The grievance procedure should be used by anyone without any concern or fear of retribution.

A grievance is not:

- A question, suggestion or general comment on the company or project; and/or
- An appeal or request for assistance.

This feedback is relevant to the Company and will be recorded as well, but such information will not be recorded as a “grievance”.

Who should be approached to submit a concern or grievance?

The CLO is the member of staff responsible for coordination of stakeholder engagement activities and the management of the grievance procedure. Grievances should be submitted in a written form directly, with the assistance of the CLO or through the grievance boxes in all communities. In the latter case, they should be referred to the CLO and kept confidential.

3.11.1 Important details

1. All formal grievances should receive a formal written reply within 10 working days, where the Company will state the date of the solution. The final response will provide additional information or, if appropriate, further instructions on proposed measures to resolve the issues;
2. All grievances should be documented. The importance of documenting all grievances is to make sure that problems are accurately understood and handled appropriately;
3. Written submissions should not be used in any way against the person or organisation submitting the complaint;
4. The names of persons submitting a grievance should be kept confidential;
5. Grievances received anonymously should be treated as comments or issues and recorded separately, but no formal response will be issued; and
6. The company should make concerted efforts to resolve grievances amicably; yet, if a grievance cannot be resolved, external experts, neutral parties or local and regional authorities, should be involved as necessary.

Written grievances may be submitted with the form on the following page or by including the following information in a letter or e-mail:

- Name;
- Organisation and position, if relevant;
- Address;
- Telephone/fax and e-mail;
- Most effective means to send a response; and
- Details of the grievance (any important details; date of the incident, location, etc.)

3.12 Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is by no means a new concept. One definition is that it relates to ensuring responsible operations during all phases of a project, considering environmental, community and human rights aspects. CSR is an evolving concept and definitions vary based on the perception of an individual and their previous experiences and geography. We are all affected by the environment and societies in which we live and work. How businesses, governments and our neighbours operate around us shapes our lives and social responsibility is the duty of individuals and businesses.

CSR is about balancing impacts on the environment and people and ensuring positive impacts are maximised; such as through local employment and engagement; and adverse environmental and social impacts are mitigated and managed. Social responsibility can be proactive; by a business taking steps to increase the positive impact it can have on the community it operates in; or it can be passive, by avoiding engaging in acts that are harmful to the environment or society. Both of these approaches to social responsibility apply to CHPM projects.

There are many ways in which corporations are 'held to account'. Beside individual legal challenges, negligence or a lack of willingness to operate responsibly can have reputational impacts. Bad publicity can have serious consequences for a company and may affect their ability to maintain existing licences, to obtain future licences, in addition to affecting their credit rating and ability to gain finance to develop projects. Social media and technology have changed the way people can access and receive information and this has been a major contributing factor to changing perceptions of how companies consider reputational risks. This technology provides a platform for companies being held accountable for their actions and gives individuals and civil society movements a 'voice'.

3.13 Education on Mineral Extraction and CHPM

Ensuring local people are educated on the need for energy and minerals should be an essential part of the stakeholder engagement process. This needs to include providing information that is easily understandable to all stakeholders, allowing people and community groups to ask questions and receive answers. This should be developed as part of the SEP and implemented before exploration work commences. It is an essential component of information public opinions and in gaining understanding and support for a development.

3.14 Conclusions of Social Impact Assessment

SIA's are usually undertaken to further a potential development by establishing social baseline conditions and then to use these to predict and manage their impacts. The purpose is to help mitigate associated risks from a project. It is also important that positive social impacts relating to the project are maximised.

In a CHPM scheme, positive social impacts include employment and community development projects, in addition to the energy and minerals produced having vital regional, national and sometimes international importance with a reduced carbon footprint. Possible concerns and negative social impacts include effects on water resources, on land use e.g. cultural heritage, recreational land use and visual impacts, noise and disturbance, harmful emissions, management drilling programmes, and the creation of ground subsidence and induced seismic events.

Whilst the specific negative and positive impacts will be unique to each site, in the present study we have outlined the typical process for completing a SIA and how stakeholders need to be engaged throughout all stages of operations, from exploration stages to closure and decommissioning of a future CHPM plant.

4 Report on Policy Implications (Task 5.4.2)

4.1 Introduction

Main aim of the CHPM2030 project lies in combination of renewable deep geothermal energy with a metal production. European Union is supporting by various schemes, platforms and directives both geothermal energy and metal production in the EU-28 countries with strategic goal towards low carbon energy production and increase of EU self-sufficiency in whole raw materials value chain.

The CHPM Energy Level (deep-geothermal, EGS) and Metal Extraction Level (a kind of in-situ leaching / in-situ recovery) seems to be a logical and effective approach, which could be technologically feasible. Currently, as a lower TRL level technology, it is too early to see clear economic feasibility. Solo EGS technology is known as a very capital-intensive technology (CHPM D5.2) with a high operational expenditures (OpEx) (Beckers et al. 2014, Mines and Nathawani 2013). The economic effect of an addition of Metal Extraction Level to the deep-geothermal EGS will be very site specific based on the natural or enhanced content of metals in geothermal brine. But the results of laboratory experiments from previous WPs (WP2 and WP3) same as the first CHPM-similar demonstration sites going online (Geo40 2019) may suggest positive steps toward economic feasibility of the CHPM technology.

From a present policy and legislative setting, the combination of both levels into one interlinked project are creating challenging issues. Platforms or project consortiums dealing with policy aspects of a deep-geothermal project development (e.g. GeoElec 2013, ETIP-DG 2018) have one common result – the whole legislative process is very complex, lengthy, and so it doesn't support a larger deployment of the deep-geothermal projects. Addition of Metal Extraction would bring other legislative duties for the developer of the CHPM plant (licensing, permitting according mining act, royalties from extracted metal etc.).

Renewable/geothermal supportive EU policy frameworks and directives are setting rather general definitions, rules and strategic goals for EU-28 countries. The EU frameworks for raw materials have a similar status. But the future of possible CHPM development will need a CHPM supportive national legislative procedure (licensing, permitting) of such costly and time-consuming combine energy/metal extraction project.

4.2 Key EU policies and regulations

Following chapter will introduce a key EU policies and regulations which can have direct or indirect influence on a possible future CHPM plant. As most of the policies and other legislative documents are regulating a specific issue, the chapter 4.2 will be divided for better clarity into four subchapters. Division will be based on Energy Level and Metal Extraction Level of the CHPM technology; policies and regulations which have an overlap to the both levels; and review of funding schemes.

4.2.1 Energy Level

Primary energy production of EU-28 shows clear rising trend of renewable energy sources and decreasing or stagnant trend of other energy sources on the other hand (Figure 3, Eurostat 2018). This change in primary energy production in the European Union can be dated since around 2000 (Figure 3) and this trend is ongoing till present. It can be stated, that this shift in energy production sources is caused by EU systematic support and promotion of renewable energy sources. A many renewable energy support and promotion documents were approved in a form of European Commission Directives, which were adopted into national energy policies of EU-28 countries.

Figure 3: Sources of EU-28 primary energy production, 1990-2016 (Eurostat 2018).

The first version of Renewable Energy Sources supporting directive (Council Directive 2011/77/EC (2001)), sometimes also called the 'RES directive', is titled as **Council Directive 2001/77/EC on the promotion of electricity produced from renewable energy sources in the internal**

electricity market. Positive correlation of renewables supporting policies with increasing energy production from renewable energy sources (RES) can be seen on the Figure 3.

The Council Directive 2011/77/EC subsequently repealed by **Council Directive 2009/28/EC (2009) on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources** introduce a clear definition of geothermal energy in the Article 2 (c): *‘geothermal energy’ means energy stored in the form of heat beneath the surface of solid earth.* Just below the ‘geothermal energy’ was the definition for ‘hydrothermal energy’ (d) which is define as: *‘energy stored in the form of heat in surface water’.* In our opinion it is strange definition, as a surface water doesn’t have too high heat capacity for energy production (definition of the ‘hydrothermal energy’ is not a part of a new directive recast). Nevertheless, the clear definition of geothermal energy should be transposed also to the national level of EU-28 countries to achieve a larger development of geothermal projects.

Beside this definition a one of the most important statement of this council directive also proposed 20 % target for the overall share of energy from renewable sources. Following the RES Directive (2009/28/EC) the policy framework ‘2020 climate & energy package’ set so called 20-20-20 targets for 2020 (European Commission 2010). The goals are to have at least 20% reduction in greenhouse emissions compared to 1990 level, 20% share of energy from renewable sources (based on consumption) and 20% increase of energy efficiency. Beside the RES directive, the individual targets were covered also in **Council Directive 2010/31/EU (2010) on the energy performance of buildings** and **Council Directive 2012/27/EU (2012) on energy efficiency.**

Geothermal energy (deep-geothermal – EGS, shallow-geothermal, district heating etc.), are very efficient renewable energy sources, which can achieve very high capacity factor (Figure 4) in comparison with other renewable energy sources, because efficiency geothermal energy sources are not influenced by external factors like sunlight, wind, etc. Thus, development of geothermal energy in EU-28 countries fits well into the EU climate & energy package.

Figure 4: Capacity factor of renewable energy sources in the U.S. for 2008 produced by National Renewable Energy Laboratory (Gelman and Hockett 2009). CSP is the Concentrated Solar Power. Geothermal energy is the most efficient renewable energy source.

The new energy policy framework, **‘Clean Energy for All Europeans’** was proposed in November 2016 and EU publication with the same name was published in May 2019 (European Commission

2019a). Also, a European strategic long-term vision ‘A Clean Planet for all’ with goal of climate-neutral Europe by 2050 was announced in 2018 (European Commission 2019b). The actions in this policy framework are in line with the Paris Agreement to keep the global temperature increase below 2°C and focus effort to keep it to 1.5°C.

This new EU climate & energy policy framework include recast (review for 2030, Figure 5) of the main renewable energy directives (Renewable Energy Directive, Energy Efficiency Directive, Energy Performance of building Directive and Eco-labelling and eco-design).

For example, the revised **Energy Efficiency Directive** (Council Directive 2018/2002/EU (2018)) is extending the energy saving obligations beyond 2020 targets by setting a new ambitious target of at least 32.5% by 2030.

Reviewed **Renewable Energy Directive** (Council Directive 2018/2001/EU (2018)) also increases target in renewable energy sources share on overall energy consumption at 32% by 2030.

Figure 5: Gradual development of EU climate and renewable energy policy framework done by ETIP-DG platform (2018).

Regarding the geothermal energy, the RED directive describes this energy source as low-to-zero emission, although it mentions that in some cases also geothermal energy can release greenhouse gases or other substances from underground fluids that can be harmful for health and the environment. Thus, the Commission requires deployment only geothermal energy with low-environmental impact. The directive also recommends Member States to assess the potential of energy from renewable sources including geothermal energy.

Another part of the '**Clean Energy for All Europeans**' policy package is an effort in a building of a Resilient Energy Union announced in 2015 (COM/2015/080). The Energy Union is concentrated on a several integrated dimensions. Its main goal in a climate action is lies in decarbonisation of the economy according conclusions of the Paris Agreement by ensure consistent reporting of the EU and its member countries under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. The Energy Union also aims on diversifying Europe's sources of energy and improving an energy efficiency. Another task of the Energy Union is to prioritize supporting of low-carbon, clean energy technology research and innovation. Larger deployment of a geothermal energy fits well in the main actions of the Energy Union.

The new regulation on **Governance of the energy union** was adopted in 2018 (European Commission 2018) and introduce framework of the national energy and climate plans (NECPs). The NECPs are building on the National renewable energy action plans 2020 The EU-28 countries have to submit their plans for the period 2021-2030 covering the strategic goals of the Energy Union and targets for 2030 set in the 'Clean Energy for All European' policy framework. All Member States already submitted their first NECP draft that will be assess and the Commission may issue recommendations for amending of their NECP by end of June 2019.

The fourth State of the energy union report published in April 2019 (European Commission 2019c) shows that EU energy supply is already safer and more accessible to everyone than it was before start of the Energy Union. The report also mentions further needs of closer cooperation of the EU institutions, Member States, local authorities, citizens and industry sector to create complete industrial value chain in low-carbon energy supply. It also emphasis importance of necessary funding to booster such innovative technological development.

The overall EU energy policy framework is setting favourable conditions for a larger development of a geothermal energy. Main task is now lying on individual Member States that should realize the potential of a geothermal energy to fulfil the 2030 and 2050 climate and energy targets. The supportive legislative mechanism allowing easier development of the geothermal energy projects is need on national/regional levels.

4.2.2 Metal Extraction Level

The Metal Extraction Level of the CHPM technology is an extraction of raw materials from primary resources, thus it has to be regulated by mineral and mining policy framework. Mineral and mining policy needs to be distinguished from each other. Simply said, mining policy sets aspects and regulations for specific exploration and mining projects (e.g. exploration and mining licences, authorizations of deep drills etc.). On the other hand, mineral policy is based on mineral consumption¹ (EU / national / regional) and considers also many other aspects (supply risk, economic situation, environment, downstream industry etc.). It is possible to say that the mining policy is in many aspects based on mineral policy. Mining policies can vary significantly from state to state, same as the national or regional level of the Member States mineral policy.

Thus, the EU raw material policy framework can be considered rather as mineral policy that is influencing mining and minerals policies on the national / regional levels. The central role in the EU raw materials policy framework is represented by the **European Innovation Partnership on Raw Materials** (EIP on Raw Materials) that is a platform connecting representatives from industry, public, governments, academia or NGOs. The EIP introduced the **Strategic Implementation Plan** (European Commission 2013) for objectives, targets and actions to be reached or implemented by 2020 (Figure 6). Overall objective of the SIP is in line with EU Industrial Policy target to increase share of industry on 20% of GDP. The SIP should contribute to the EU Industrial Policy target by reducing import and enhancing Member state production and export of raw materials. Supply conditions for growth of EU industry should be also supported by diversifying raw materials sourcing and improving resource efficiency via innovative mining methods, recycling or substitution.

¹ Mineral consumption (MS) = (primary and secondary) production + imports – exports (EU / national / regional MS)

Figure 6: Infographic of the EIP’s Strategic Implementation Plan

The EIP is directly connected to a key (and one of the first) EU legislative document aiming to promote and support mineral industry sector – the **Raw Material Initiative COM(2008)669** (European Commission 2008). RMI, a policy framework aiming to secure raw materials supply for the EU, is consisting of three pillars: 1) *Fair and sustainable supply of raw materials from global markets* (raw materials diplomacy, support for SMEs); 2) *Sustainable supply of raw materials within the EU* (national minerals policy indicators, knowledge base – e.g. Raw Material Information System,, exchange of best practices in mineral industry, research and innovation – CHPM project partially belong here); and 3) *Resource efficiency and supply of 'secondary raw materials' through recycling* (eco-design, trade in waste).

European Commission (2011) also defined the list of ‘critical raw materials’ (CRM) which are necessary for the industry and healthy economy in the EU (Figure 8). The list is updated every three years (2014, 2017).

Figure 7: Critical Raw Materials – 2017 criticality assessment. Green dots represent both critical and non-critical raw materials proven to be recoverable by CHPM extraction technology. Edited after Deloitte Sustainability et al. (2017).

In general, definition and methodology of CRM is based on two variables: 1) economic importance calculated from the share of consumption of raw material in end-use sector and the sector's gross value added; and 2) supply risk, variable with formula, uses rate of substitutability, recycling rate, production shares by country and Economic and political stability by country.

Beside exploration and extraction of primary resources, EU policy framework is aiming to support whole 'value chain' and 'circular economy' (Figure 7). General objective is to keep ideally a full value chain closest to the primary resource (extraction, processing and, in best cases also manufacturing of a products). The CHPM concept fit well into this strategy, as the CHPM plant would produce raw materials together with a renewable electricity and heat to supply the next steps of value chain (raw materials production, manufacturing, etc.).

Emphasis on Eco-design products and efficiency recycling should contribute to the increase of secondary resources and thus closing a loop of circular economy.

Figure 8: Raw materials and its value chain – circular economy infographic (ERA-MIN 2 2017)

4.2.3 EU policies and regulations for both levels

Despite fact that a future CHPM plant should be a low-to-zero emission technology; exploration and development of such plant will have a certain impact on the environment and the society. The impacts have to be assessed with an uttermost caution as any possible neglected impact can cause society distrust in the new technology and so its development can be retarded or even impossible.

The Council Directive 2001/42/EC (2001), the SEA Directive ('on the assessment of the effects of certain plans and programmes on the environment'), belongs among the first comprehensive legislative framework that set rules for high level protection of the environment, define which

strategic policy, plans and programmes should carry an environmental assessment and define structure and timing of an environmental report. The report has to be done at the end of the plan/programme evaluation assessing possible significant effects on the environment, biodiversity, population, human health, flora, fauna, soil, water, air, climate or cultural heritage.

Next environmental protection document is the **EIA Directive ('on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment')** that came into force in 2011 (**Council Directive 2011/92/EU**), later amended by **Council Directive 2014/52/EU**). In contrast with the SEA directive that is regulating strategic policy plans and programmes, the EIA directive is aimed on environmental assessment of certain public and private projects listed in the directive's Annexes I and II. Deep geothermal drilling is listed among Extractive Industry in the Annex II and the EIA directive give Member State option to determine whether such projects should carry and EIA. The determination process should be made through a) a case-by-case examination or (b) by a certain thresholds or criteria set by the Member state. Examples of the national legislative shows that the threshold is in some cases set on the targeted depth of the drilling, planned electricity/thermal capacity or the size of the surface development. But CHPM approach is aiming to ultra-deep metal enrichment and also plan to extract metals, which is subject to an Article 4(1) and the EIA have to be done for this kind of projects.

Assessment of any possible impacts of the CHPM plant was covered in Task 5.5, resulting in detailed report **D5.5 Environmental impact assessment framework**. The both EIA and SEA Directive is focused also on effects that can influence local communities. Strategy how to avoid public opposition was described in detail in the Chapter 3 (Task 5.4.1). Thus, both EIA and SEA will not be described in detail and other key policies or regulations related to the CHPM plant will be further discussed.

Local communities are very sensitive when the groundwater quality or quantity are mention as possible impact. Targets of the deep-geothermal wells are well below groundwater reservoirs, but the same situation was e.g. in targets of shale-gas exploration and many of the public concerns, which eventually led politicians to ban the exploration in some Member States, were about the groundwater sources.

All water bodies (both surface and underground) are protected by the 'EU Water Framework Directive' (**Council Directive 2000/60/EC establishing a framework for the Community action in the field of water policy**) came into force in 2000. In 2006, 'a daughter groundwater directive (**Council Directive 2006/118/EC on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration**) was introduced. The main goal of both directives aims on the 'good status' of all water bodies in the EU. WFD propose assess of water quality based on biological, hydromorphological, physical-chemical and chemical

quality criteria. The allowance of reinjection into same aquifer of water used by geothermal operations is very important and supportive regulation for EGS and CHPM development.

CHPM facility will have an advantage against other extraction industry plants in the waste management. The CHPM extraction technology would produce very low to none mining waste like other mining industry processing plants. Nevertheless, if there would be any 'waste' (e.g. some type of a tailings of waste solids or slurries that remain after the treatment of metal from geothermal brine) from the CHPM extraction or processing technology it would have to be regulated according **Mining Waste Directive (Council Directive 2006/21/EC (2006))**. The directive requires that mining and quarry operators take all measures necessary to prevent or reduce any adverse environmental or human health effects related to the management of extractive waste and development of the waste management plan. Question is whether the CHPM facility could be define as a mining facility.

Second option is that the CHPM extraction technology could fall under the **Industrial Emissions Directive (Council Directive 2010/75/EU(2010))**, which have to be obey in case of facilities which: "Processing of non-ferrous metals, production of non-ferrous crude metals from ore, concentrates or secondary raw materials by metallurgical, chemical or electrolytic processes". It is probable that such definition would be valid for use of mild leaching reagents (experiments in CHPM WP2) in the stimulated reservoir.

Such process is a type of ISL (in-situ leaching) or ISR (in-situ recovery) mining/extraction method that is not yet clearly define in EU or national legislative (BIOMore 2016), because such mining method is not currently used in the EU. Projects like CHPM (extraction of metals from fluid on a physico-chemical basis) or BIOMore (in-situ extraction from ore bodies on biological basis) are developing innovative ('cleaner alternative to conventional') mining method which suffer from lack of a specific legislation cover.

The ISL method would probably fall under a set of principles that have to be considered in such processing plant (e.g. 'the necessary measures are taken to prevent accidents and limit their consequences'; 'No significant pollution is caused'; and strict compliance of the **Waste Framework Directive (Council Directive 2008/98/EC (2008))**).

The **Industrial Emissions Directive (2010/75/EU)** is supportive for new concepts by following statement: (Industrial Emissions Directive) "*do not apply to research or development activities, or the testing of new products and processes*". But, the lack of legislative cover could slow down the larger and commercial deployment of such innovative mining methods.

The new concepts using a stimulation of a reservoir (e.g. geothermal reservoirs or deep ore bodies) and use of a leaching have to be consider a possible risk of induced micro-seismic events. This

environmental impact which exceptionally occurred also during EGS development (e.g. Basel, Switzerland EGS Project; Pohang South Korea EGS project) has very negative influence on public acceptance of such type of geothermal projects. The microseismic event with a magnitude 3.4 occurred in Basel EGS project in 2006 (Wyss and Rybach 2010). Following the event, many other EGS projects were terminated. This situation led to the creation of EU-funded research platform **GEISIR (Geothermal Engineering Integrating Mitigation of Induced Seismicity in Reservoirs)**. The project came with recommendations how to mitigate the risk of microseismic events occurrence. Risk of microseismic events during EGS/CHPM development is highly sensitive issue that have to be carefully assess, because this risk can lead to suspension of the project (e.g. Pohang EGS, Grigoli et al. 2018), increasing of mistrust or in the worst case to the termination of EGS development in certain country. On the other hand, the Switzerland experienced two majors induced microseismic events – Basel EGS project in 2006 (Wyss and Rybach 2010) and newer St. Gallen deep geothermal project in 2013 (Diehl et al. 2017), yet the Switzerland **policy incentives (feed-in-tariff)** for deep geothermal projects development are one of the highest in Europe on €0.48/kWh for petrothermal (hot-dry rock, EGS) projects (Geothermie-Schweiz 2018).

4.2.4 EU Funding Incentives

The innovative projects have a disadvantage against conventional ones (no matter if we are speaking about mining or energy production operations) in lack of necessary funds for projects development. The innovative and commercially untested technological projects are bearing a higher risk threatening the investment in case of project failure. Especially projects that have to deal with uncertain situation beneath the surface (e.g. district heating, deep drilling for both geothermal and mining purposes) have to consider so called ‘geological risk’ (Suslick and Schiozer 2004, Danube Transnational Programme 2016). EU banks and other financial institutions are looking on low to zero risk projects and significantly risky projects in mineral exploration, mining or also geothermal exploration have problems to secure funds for capital-intensive projects.

EU has a several funding programs that can be applied especially on development of innovative technologies which can contribute to fulfil targets set by ‘Clean Energy for All European’ policy framework. The fourth report of the State of the Energy Union (European Commission 2019c) concludes that securing of necessary funding will be a key to reach the targets for 2030. Deployment of renewable geothermal energy or also low-to-zero emission/waste metal extraction technology that can cause reduction in high-emission conventional mining facilities could fit well into such programs.

The NER 300 is funding programme that is using incomes from EU Emission Trading Scheme (ETS) for support of innovative renewable energy or carbon-capture storage projects (CCS). A several geothermal projects were awarded by support from NER300 since first call in 2012 (e.g. the South Hungarian EGS Demonstration, GEOSTRAS project (EGS, France, Strasbourg) or Geothermae project (conventional geothermal, Croatia)). From 2020 onwards, the NER300 will be replaced by an Innovation Fund Programme (European Commission 2019d)

Another financial support applicable for geothermal projects is the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), based on EU Cohesion Policy. 'Cohesion policy' is the policy behind the hundreds of thousands of projects all over Europe that receive funding from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund (ESF) and the Cohesion Fund (Cohesion Fund applies to EU Member States which have a GDP lower than 90 % of the EU-27 average – Croatia not taken into account). Thus, economic and social cohesion is about 'reducing disparities between the various regions and the backwardness of the least-favoured regions' (European Commission 2019e). These regions have often also lower share of renewable energy sources on electricity production.

European Investment Bank (EIB) is the bank of the European Union that is owned by Member States and act according EU and Member States policy priorities. Financial support of a 'climate action' projects has the highest priority accounting currently 29% of total EIB lending strategy (EIB 2019).

Horizon 2020 is the biggest EU research and innovation funding programme with almost €80 billion funding (2014-2020) for projects that would increase Europe's global competitiveness in various topic in science, industry or tackling societal challenges. Many projects with focus on innovative mining methods and geothermal energy got financial support from H2020 programme.

4.3 Policy implications for CHPM project development phases

A future process of CHPM plant development will combine procedure deep-geothermal energy project with a mining industry project. The both geothermal energy and mining project have many things in common (compare Figure 8 and Figure 9). Both types of projects start with a very high risk that is gradually decreasing with increasing knowledge and status of exploration. Mining and geothermal projects are typical intensive-capital cost projects with long development time during which the company has not any income. Thus, financing of such specific projects is subject of a great risk with possible very high reward, but with uncertain result from beginning. Financing of such projects in Europe is not easy, bank and financial institutions are not used to highly risk projects and, in many cases, are not willing to support such kind of projects. Here, the geothermal energy projects (that are labelled as a ‘clean renewable projects’) have a certain advantage than mineral exploration or mining projects that are, in many cases, perceived as a ‘unclean industry’ and thus can have different rate in public acceptance and investment attractiveness.

The Life Cycle of a Mine

Figure 9: A life cycle schematic sketch of a mining project (Holmes 2014). Phases (and in many cases also timetable) of a mining project are almost identical with those of a deep-geothermal project when comparing with Figure 9. Notice that the mining project sketch (as a mature commercial industry) contains also projection into share price (Y axe).

The whole development of CHPM project can be divided into three stages; ‘Exploration’, ‘Development’ and ‘In operation’ (Figure 8). Individual stages bear different rate of risk, cost and time.

	Year 0	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8
Status	UNDER INVESTIGATION			UNDER DEVELOPMENT				IN OPERATION	
Prefeasibility	Services								
Exploration		Exploration and test drilling							
Resource development				Drilling					
Construction					Engineering and Construction				
Commission and operating									Operation & Maintenance

Figure 10: Three main phases (status) of a geothermal project with timetable and more detailed description of development works (EGEC 2019). The same scenario could be considered for CHPM plant.

- 1) Exploration – developing company have to obtain exploration licence and start with exploration work that end (in positive cases) with identification of geothermal reservoir and, in case of CHPM, also with finding of ‘EGS orebody’ as well. Some preliminary resource estimation and pre-feasibility study should take place at the end of this stage.
- 2) Development – if the (pre)feasibility was proven and developing company secured financing for capital intensive ‘construction’ of CHPM plant, the development stage begins. Environmental and related social impact is highest during the construction (development stage). The development stage should end with successfully performer technology test.
- 3) In operation / production – the technology is tested; company have to secure access to national grid. Start of energy (electricity and heat) generation and metal extraction. The company is starting to sell products, pays the investments and do all necessary maintenance works.

4.3.1 Exploration phase

The exploration phase starts with a plan or more exactly with a business plan on developing a CHPM plant in a ‘potential area’. The potential can be assessed from different point of views – probably the most important is a ‘geological’ point of view – a theoretical potential for deep-geothermal energy (temperature gradient, type of rock etc.) combined with an ore body or metal enriched rock. Other ‘point of views’, including policy aspects, are not of less importance. Developing company have to strongly consider a local (national / regional) policy framework that regulate renewable geothermal energy and extractive/mining industry. Underestimation of policy

consideration can result into end of the project in early or worse in later stage of project development, when costly exploration and developing works already began.

The first in row is the ownership of the resource – both geothermal and mineral resource. The most common situation in Europe is resource ownership by a State or ‘Crown’ (in case of a monarchy). It means that the surface above the resource is own by a landowner but resource itself is a possession of a State/Crown. In the second situation landowner owns also a resource. That could be a problematic situation in larger resources where the surface above the resource is owned by many landowners and a developer would have to buy or rent (+ request for exploration) a land from all of them. Some States hold ownership only on the mineral deposits of higher importance (various definitions across Member States e.g. 1st category, medallic, onshore, deeper than 6 m, etc.), other are in private hands.

Geothermal resource on itself and the ownership is defined clearly only in some Member states, especially those that are already developing geothermal energy and thus the legislative was updated (e.g. Germany, France). In other countries the geothermal resources and its ownership is still poorly defined. National levels updates of the basic definition of geothermal energy as it is described in Council Directive 2009/28/EC (2009) on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources would be the highly recommended as the first step toward larger deployment of geothermal energy. Also, an EGS concept should be defined in acts that are regulating extraction of geothermal energy. Our opinion on an EGS definition of Dumas et al. (2013): “an underground reservoir that has been created or improved artificially” is agreeable.

Challenging issue could be a situation when the geothermal resource is owned by a landowner and State owns the mineral resource. The State ownership of both geothermal and mineral resource seems to be the best option which would be helpful for future development of a CHPM projects. But it is on national governments strategical decisions to update it for sake of larger deployment of deep-geothermal/CHPM projects.

The CHPM developer should carefully consider the risk and cost of the CHPM project before start of licensing process. The CHPM project will be a very similar to a mineral exploration/mining projects that are considered as one of the riskiest business. The CHPM project will be very capital intensive and the first income will come (in positive cases) after some 5-10 years. Prior that there will be only very high expenditures. The first exploration stage is not so capital intensive in comparison with a second development stage, but the risk, especially the ‘geological risk’ is the highest (Figure 10). Only more and more verification exploration works can significantly reduce the risk. However, such verification works are very expensive and the developer company and the company (e.g. in case

of some small junior exploration company) have not their own finance. It means that they must secure money from private sources (stock exchange) or some governmental/institutional incentives (e.g. national or EU level grants).

As a geothermal exploration (especially deep-geothermal) is still commercially unmaturing, some countries introduced a ‘geothermal risk insurance fund’ that can partially cover exploration drilling costs in case of unsuccessful wells. If a CHPM developer company would apply for such kind of insurance mechanism, they can be more successful in securing funds. Examples of such geothermal risk insurance fund are GEODEEP risk insurance fund in France (Mancheva 2015) or Risk Sharing Mechanism in Turkey (Turkey Geothermal Risk Sharing Mechanism 2018). The GeoElec project (Fraser et al. 2013) described in detail possible introduction of Geothermal Risk Insurance Fund at the EU level that could help to larger deployment of geothermal energy projects in the EU. However, it is important to notice that such kind of insurance are not common in commercially mature mineral exploration business, thus it is ambiguous whether the CHPM concept that combine both businesses could apply to a geothermal insurance mechanism.

Geothermal Project Risk and Cumulative Investment Cost

Figure 11: Graphical display of project risk and cumulative cost of a geothermal project (Gehring and Loksha 2012). A mining project would yield a very similar picture.

After considering geological (geothermal, mineral) potential from available information (e.g. older exploration and research works) and considering also ownership, financing and risk, the CHPM

developing company must request a relevant national or regional government office for an exploration licence. This process is again very specific from state to state; a many older but also recent studies (Goodman et al. 2010, GeoElec 2013, ETIP DG 2018a, ETIP DG 2018b) reported a difficult and lengthy legislative process from most of the Member States which does not help to deployment of geothermal projects. Various government offices on both national, regional and very local level have to express their approval, disapproval or request conditions for exploration licensing. A call for unifying process in (developer would communicate only with one office that would address all ministries or other government institutes – so called 'one-stop-shop') and definition of geothermal energy position in different national codes (mining, water, waste, environmental, etc.) but also in EU level communications and directives would be a very supportive step.

A deep-geothermal EGS concept is very specific as the stimulated reservoir could be a very large when displaying on the surface and exploration licence fee is in most cases based on fixed value for every square km started on annual basis. Thus, a very large exploration area would be another financial burden for exploration/developing company. But it is very difficult if not impossible to know a size of future stimulated reservoir in the phase of exploration license request. An option could be an exploration area which borders would be set around location of planned exploration boreholes.

CHPM project would have to combine both mineral and geothermal exploration already in this stage. These two exploration targets should be included in one interlinked exploration licence. This could be another challenging issue as most of the Member States are safeguarding the mineral deposits/resources (even the potential ones) by limiting other activities that could cause conflict of interest in case of future exploitation of the mineral resource. Many national codes specifically define these activities and not uncommonly the other than mineral exploration (including geothermal, carbon-capture storage – CCS, underground nuclear-waste storages) must not interfere to the safeguarded deposit. However, CHPM concept is aiming also on mineral deposit, even it does not have to be a mineral deposit in 'general sense', but also a metal/mineral enriched rocks that could not be mined economically conventional methods. Also, for this purpose a term 'EGS-orebody' could be introduced/define. An EGS orebody would be a target (exploration licence) for CHPM technology (both mineral and geothermal) that is not degrade mineral deposit; conversely the CHPM concept intends to exploit the mineral deposit according mining act, related regulations and State mineral policy strategies. One possibility of the EGS-orebody definition could be (with use of EGS definition by Dumas et al. 2013): "an underground reservoir in metal enriched rocks that has been created or improved artificially".

An orebody/reservoir for a CHPM purposes should be described and defined during exploration works. If the exploration goes well and a very potential CHPM reservoir was discovered, additional exploration works (drilling, well logging, surface geophysics etc.) and techno-economic factors of possible future CHPM plant should be assessed. Preliminary EIA and SIA have to be integral part of exploration work same as a stakeholder engagement from the beginning (as described in Task 5.4.1). In such positive cases the first exploration stage should be finished by feasible study that have to present a commercial maturity of the project and thus can ‘lure’ investors willing to give their money for next development step in expectations of future profits.

To avoid speculations (intentionally data distortion or overestimation to raise money from investors) the both geothermal and mineral resources should be presented in compliance with internationally recognized reporting code. There is very good opportunity for combination of geothermal energy and metal extraction level, because all proposals for geothermal reporting codes are based on mineral reserves and resources reporting codes (CRIRSCO, JORC). This suggests the possibility to report both mineral and geothermal resources of CHPM project under one reporting codes. Probably the first Geothermal Reserves and Resources Reporting code was established in the Australia (Lawless et al. 2010), where the private investment in risky exploration is very common and thus investors called for a reporting code for which they are used in financing of mineral exploration. The Australian Geothermal Code is largely based on JORC code (Figure 11), using volumetric method (also in case of reservoir stimulation) to define Indicated or Measured Resources and Proven or Probable Reserves (Lawless et al. 2010).

Figure 12: Relationship between Exploration Results, Geothermal Resources and Geothermal Reserves (Lawless et al. 2010). The Key JORC diagram looks entirely same only with exception of Exploration Resources and Ore Reserves.

Canadian geothermal industry was built on the Australian reporting code (Tryggvadóttir 2013); also, in Canada the private investment for exploration projects exploration companies listed on stock exchange are common situation. The Europe is not used so much on the fully private investment of exploration an exploration companies listed on stock exchanges; possible also because that there are not such strong calls for a geothermal reporting code (in comparison with call for insurance risk mechanism). Europe bet on ‘waiting strategy’, will be observing Australian and Canadian experience with the codes and established geothermal working group to contribute with topic on geothermal energy resources to UNFC-2009 classification (Tryggvadóttir 2013, Geothermal Working Group 2016). However, future shifting of deep-geothermal and CHPM to commercial level will need national or better internationally recognized code.

4.3.2 Development phase

If we will stay with comparison with mineral exploration to look for possible commercial environment, the development phase would start when the geothermal/mineral resources (or better reserves – depend on how intensive a successful was the first exploration stage) are confirmed by an owner (e.g. State committees for mineral resources) and developing of a mine/geothermal plant can thus begin. For this a detailed plan of development work, techno-economic aspects, EIA is commonly required.

The development phases bear lower risk in comparison with the first exploration stage, but the investment costs (CAPEX) are dramatically increasing (Figure 10). It means that CHPM developer company (based on results from exploration and feasibility study) have to secure much more financial resources to develop the project. For this, a ‘competitive window’ like in mining industry could be advised. A ‘competitive window’ can be define as time frame (around 1 year) after the confirmation of reserves/resources, when no other than a company which run the exploration can request for licence to develop a mine/geothermal plant on the discovered and confirmed reserves/resources. This can allow the developing company to secure financial resources and prepare detailed developing plan.

The plan must strongly consider social impact assessment, because in this stage the impact for the society and environment will be highest. The main wells must be drilled, and stimulation of the reservoir have to be done in this stage. Also, surface technological components have to be constructed. Strict compliance with all environmental, water and waste regulations (EIA, CHPM D5.5) must be respected to prevent creation of public opposition.

Drilling of the main well doublet and reservoir stimulation works should also lead to refining a resource estimation toward defining proven geothermal/mineral reserves. Only such defined

reserves allow more precise economic modelling and estimation of future incomes which will be critical for secure (and hold) private investments or other means of funds (governmental/institutional grants, incentives, loans).

The development phase can take quite a long time (e.g. up to 5 year estimated by EGEC 2019, Figure 9) and still no income, on the contrary the expenditures can overcome a \$100M (CHPM D5.2 annex). At the end of the development phase, the both surface and underground technology segments are constructed and test of the CHPM plant prove its fully operational status.

4.3.3 Commissioning and production phase

If the all technological segments of the CHPM plant were successfully tested, the production phase can begin. The valid mining licence is needed for production phase, if the company has enough information on production (capacity, targeted metals, etc.), it can be possible to apply for mining licence already together with 'developing' license.

The access to the national grid and agreement with the operator/State on the contract of electricity generation is crucial for success of the project. The support for renewable energy is fixed in RES directive (COM2018/2001/EU) in Article 2 (b):

“Member States shall also provide for either priority access or guaranteed access to the grid-system of electricity produced from renewable energy sources”

Policy aspects play also an important role in the contract, as many Member States are providing support to renewable via 'feed-in-tariff' or 'premiums'. In simply way, feed-in-tariff means payments per kilowatt-hour for electricity generated from a renewable source. Incentives in form of feed-in-tariff have longer history in case of solar a wind energy sources, but more European countries introduced feed-in-tariff also for geothermal energy. Interestingly for EGS, some countries established so-called petrothermal bonus (unconventional geothermal, hot-dry rock – the EGS concept), mostly in range of 0.0X €/kWh. Such bonus should be perceived as supportive incentive for the higher capital expenditures of an EGS project in comparison with conventional geothermal project. For example, Switzerland recently (2018) set probably the highest feed-in-tariff in the Europe on €0.42/kWh generated from geothermal energy source (≤ 5 MW) and €0.49/kWh from geothermal energy source with a petrothermal bonus. For comparison, Germany set feed-in-tariff on €0.25/kWh and e.g. France has geothermal feed-in-tariff on €0.2/kWh + energy efficiency bonus on €0.08/kWh. Italy which is leading EU member state in geothermal electricity production with more than 800 MW_e installed capacity has feed-in-tariff in similar rate as Germany or France (€0.2/kWh), however it is limited only to a 'power plants' up to 1 MW that is too small for a commercial project.

Another policy implication for this stage are the royalties. If the geothermal/mineral resources would be state owned, the company that will be extracting metals or energy must pay royalties to the owner. Royalties in mining industry is a common thing and in most of the cases are calculated in percentages (commonly 1-10%) from a market price of a produced raw material/metal. Questionable will be royalty for geothermal energy production, especially in EGS case (hot-dry rock) which is using an 'artificial reservoir' that continuously supplemented by extracted geothermal brine via injection well and heated by interior heat of the Earth core. Some project consortiums (GeoElec – Dumas et al. 2013 or Goodman et al. 2010, GTR-H – Goodman et al. 2010) are suggesting that royalties for geothermal energy should be kept as low as possible which is also a good signal to for larger deployment of a deep-geothermal and thus also CHPM projects.

4.4 Conclusions of Policy Implications

In general sense, EU directives, policy frameworks, strategies and funding schemes established a supportive environment for research, innovation projects and development of pilot projects in renewable geothermal energy and low-impact mining/metal extraction methods.

Directives clearly define some principal terms (definition of geothermal energy, reijection of geothermal brine etc.) that are fundamental for development of deep-geothermal projects (thus also EGS and CHPM projects). However, other terms still must be defined to achieve larger and commercial deployment of a geothermal projects same as future CHPM projects that are largely based on EGS concept. Some of these terms that lack clear definition is the EGS (possible definition by Dumas et al. 2013: "an underground reservoir that has been created or improved artificially") or EGS-orebody that can be possibly define with use of abovementioned definition as: "an underground reservoir in metal enriched rocks that has been created or improved artificially".

The EU policy is reflecting the innovations in both geothermal and mineral industry sector. However, minerals policy, supply of raw materials and licensing for development of CHPM projects fall under the competence of individual Member states jurisdiction. Here, the main 'challenge' for a CHPM project development will be the conflict of interest between extractive (mining) industry regulations and renewable geothermal energy regulations. Unifying of deep-geothermal (EGS) and innovative metal extraction methods developed in the CHPM project under one licensing and regulatory authority (possibly the Member state's mining authority) and single resource ownership will be key aspects for a future development of the CHPM technology.

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